

Viscosity B -Coefficients and Partial Molar Volumes of Known Drugs (as Salts)

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Viscosity B -coefficients of a number of drugs (viz. hydrochlorides of cyproheptadine, chlorpromazine, ethambutol, amodiaquin and pheniramine maleate) in water have been determined at three different temperatures (293, 298 and 303 K). The single ion B_{\pm} values have been found to be high and positive but the B_{\pm}/dT values have been found to be negative. All drug cations can be regarded to be highly structure-making in character and highly solvated. This is due to hydrophobic hydrations of the drug molecules. The activation parameters have been found to be very high and positive. Naturally, the drug diffusion through the solution is extremely slow. The partial molar volumes of the drug molecules have been found to be high.

Drug action has been widely recognized to be the ultimate consequence of physicochemical interactions between the drug and functionally important molecules in the living organism known as receptor¹⁻³. Drug-receptor interaction is necessarily complex involving a number of physicochemical interactions, like ionic and covalent bonding, ion-dipole interactions, charge transfer, hydrogen-bonding, hydrophobic interactions etc.¹⁻³. However, drug action is not always mediated by receptors. A number of non-specific physicochemical interactions and non-specific effects like solubility, lipid solubility, pK_a or pK_b values, osmolarity, membrane penetration, i.e. transport of drug ions through the biomembranes etc. are also important to understand drug action⁴.

It is to be noted that drug action can be achieved with a small amount of drugs as high concentrations are rarely achieved *in vivo*, therefore, drug transport and ion-solvent interactions are the controlling forces in dilute solution where ion-ion interactions are absent. It is natural to believe that the structures of the drugs are modified by the solvent or even the structure of the solvent may be modified by the drugs. Thus, the information regarding the transport property of drugs and the ion-solvent interactions may be obtained from viscosity measurements. A compilation of such data may be helpful for a possible correlation between drug activities and viscosities.

Studies of the partial molar volume of electrolytes of drug molecules have been useful to understand ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions. This is particularly true for the apparent molar volumes at infinite dilution where ion-ion interactions are absent⁵. But studies on the viscosity and partial molar volumes of the drugs have been rarely attempted. These considerations led us to study the viscosity and partial molar volumes of available water-soluble drugs (hydrochlorides of cyproheptadine, chlorpromazine, ethambutol, amodiaquin and pheniramine maleate) of varied nature.

Results and Discussion

The data have been analyzed using the Jones-Dole equation⁶,

$$(\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

where $\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0$; η_r and η represent the relative viscosity and viscosity of the solution, η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, C the molar concentration, and A and B are characteristic constants specific to the ion and the solvent. The $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$, concentration (C) and density (ρ) values of different electrolytes are reported in Table 1.

The equation (1) has been modified to

$$(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{\theta C} = A' + B'\sqrt{\theta C} \quad (3)$$

for associated electrolytes like pheniramine maleate, amodiaquin dihydrochloride. The θ values of the associated electrolytes at different concentrations have been calculated using K_A values⁷ of the electrolytes determined conductometrically.

The plots of $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ against \sqrt{C} or $\sqrt{\theta C}$ have been found to be linear without scatter in the concentration ranges studied. Three typical plots are presented in Figs. 1-3. In general, a least-square treatment has been utilized to obtain A - and B -values. The values of the slopes have been accepted if the regression coefficient is better than 0.99. The intercepts have been found to be positive. The A -values, calculated theoretically using Falkenhagen-Vernon equation⁸,

$$A_{\text{theor}} = \frac{0.2577\Lambda_0}{\eta_0(\epsilon T)^{1/2}\lambda_+^0\lambda_-^0} \left[1 - 0.6863 \left(\frac{\lambda_+^0 - \lambda_-^0}{\Lambda_0} \right)^2 \right] \quad (4)$$

are given in Table 2 (where possible). The λ_+^0 , λ_-^0 and Λ_0^0 values of the electrolytes determined by us have been utilized⁹. However, in view of non-availability of λ_{\pm}^0 data at different temperatures, the experimental A -values have been preferred. The temperature coefficient of A -values have been known to be small.

where η is the absolute viscosity, ρ the density and t the efflux time of water. The values of the characteristic constants of the viscometer, K and L are 5.01×10^{-3} and 1.0216 respectively. The calibration of the viscometer was checked periodically by measuring the flow times with water at three temperatures and the ratio K/L was found to be constant during the course of the work. Runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within 0.1 s. No kinetic energy corrections were made.

Stock solutions of each salt were prepared by weight and the working solutions obtained by appropriate dilution. The solubility of the salts varied with the nature of the drugs. In most cases the concentration ranges were limited to $0.002 < M < 0.15$. The flow time of the drug solutions was measured as described above. Density was measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer (29.3927 ml), which was previously calibrated using triple-distilled water.

Both viscosity and density measurements were made in a water thermostat maintained at desired temperatures controlled to ± 0.01 . The accuracy of density and viscosity measurements are $3.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg dm}^{-3}$ and $4.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The viscosity was calculated using equation (15). The viscosity and density data of water had been taken from the literature²³.

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TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN DIFFERENT ETHANOL-WATER MEDIA

EtOH %(v/v)	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger
[Co(BigH) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ³⁺ + Aspartic acid ^a :		
10	73.67	-106.7
20	64.88	-94.0
30	61.13	-106.7
[Co(BigH) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ³⁺ + Glutamic acid ^b :		
10	55.5(6.5)	-145.0(19.9)
20	47.0(6.5)	-170.0(19.9)
30	38.0(5.2)	-193.0(15.9)

^aRef. 4. ^bPresent work.Values in the parenthesis reflect the SD against each ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger .

with quite large negative values of ΔS^\ddagger are diagnostic of an I_a mechanism.

The small decrease in values of ΔH^\ddagger with lowering the dielectric constant of the media can be justified by the fact that a medium of lower dielectric constant enhances the reaction rate by decreasing the electrostriction of the medium. In consequence, the force operating between the triply charged complex and the solvent molecule is lowered, thus helping the reacting ions to acquire greater freedom and thus requiring less activation energy⁷. Biguanide [BigH = H₂NC(NH)NHC(NH)NH₂] is an unsaturated ligand having a π -bonding in the bis-chelate, and removes electron cloud from Co^{II} centres through the t_{2g} orbitals, thus facilitating the tendency of these orbitals to accommodate the incoming ligand and a significant amount of bond formation in the transition state occurs before bond cleavage in the process. A compact transition state between [Co(BigH)₂(H₂O)]³⁺ and

LH is formed by the outersphere association, stabilized possibly through H-bonding as shown in Fig. 2. This is also reflected in the increase in rate in solvent of lower dielectric constant where the outersphere association is more favoured.

Experimental

cis-[Co(BigH)₂(H₂O)](ClO₄)₃ (Complex 1) was prepared by literature method⁸. A freshly prepared 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ solution (pH 3.6) of complex 1 exhibited λ_{\max} at 490 nm, agreeable to the data already reported⁸. The reaction product between [Co(BigH)₂(H₂O)](ClO₄)₃ and glutamic acid was prepared by mixing them in 1 : 1 molar ratio in 10% (v/v) ethanol-water and refluxing the mixtures for 20 h. The solid reaction product in the form of glittering rosy crystals separated out on concentration. The product was repeatedly washed with absolute alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator until constant weight. The absorption spectrum of a freshly prepared 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ solution (pH 3.6) of the product recorded by a Beckman spectrophotometer, exhibited λ_{\max} at 490 nm. The stoichiometry of the product, confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation, was found to contain 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio. Semimicro analytical technique was adopted for elemental analysis of the product : (Found : C, 17.20; H, 3.87; N, 25.50; Co, 9.70; Cl, 11.67. Calcd. for : C, 17.80; H, 3.80; N, 24.90; Co, 9.80 and Cl, 11.80%). The elemental analysis was in good conformity of the composition of the product with the molecular formula [Co(BigH)₂L](ClO₄)₂ (Complex 2).

The course of the reaction was followed by a Beckman spectrophotometer at 490 nm, where a substantial difference existed in the absorbances of Complex 1 and

Fig. 2. Probable mechanism of the reaction process.

the salts have been found to be predominantly positive but small indicating the existence of small ion-ion interactions. The viscosity B -coefficients of the salts are fairly high. This is rational in view of large size of the amphipathic molecules. The molecules have a number of hydrophobic sites for interactions. Naturally, the ion-solvent interactions appear to be high. The contribution of first term of eqn. (6) to B is negative but the contribution is swamped by the large positive values of the second term, i.e. $\Delta\mu_2^\circ$ values are expected to be fairly high. Though B -coefficients give some idea regarding ion-solvent interaction but for better understanding, it is desirable to subdivide B -coefficients into ionic contributions. A number of methods have been suggested and the methods are usually based on the assumption that the cation and anion of particular salts behave identically in solution. Following the suggestion of Kaminsky¹³, Kay *et al.*¹⁴, considered $B_{K^+} = B_{Cl^-}$ at all temperatures and divided B -coefficients into separate components. Sacco *et al.*¹⁵ used $B_{BPh_4^-} = B_{PPH_4^+}$ for subdivision. The single ions obtained by the methods obviously differ both qualitatively and quantitatively. However, due to similarity

and quantitative closeness between the single ion values with $B_{K^+} = B_{Cl^-}$ and $B_{PPh_4^-} = B_{BPh_4^+}$ (Ref. 15), the value $B_{K^+} = B_{Cl^-} = -0.007$ at all temperatures has been used in the present calculation. The single ion values of drug cation except pheniramine cation are given in Table 3b. The single ion value for maleate ion is not available. The results suggest that $dB_+/dT < 0$ and $B_+ > 0$ for drug ions indicate that the drugs usually behave as structure-makers though the counter ion Cl^- is a structure-breaker^{13,16}. The structure-making behavior obviously arises due to hydrophobic interactions.

The ionic B -coefficients have been found to be high

TABLE 3b—VISCOSITY B_+ COEFFICIENTS, $-(dB_+/dT)$ AND SOLVATION NUMBERS (η_s) OF THE CATIONS OF DRUG SALTS

Drugs as	B_+ ($dm^3 mol^{-1}$) values based on $B_{K^+} = B_{Cl^-}$			$-(dB_+/dT)$	η_s
	293 K	298 K	303 K		
hydrochlorides					
Cyproheptadine	2.287	2.019	1.714	0.0573	35(3)
Chlorpromazine	1.327	1.176	1.143	0.0184	18(7)
Ethambutol	2.444	2.185	2.067	0.0377	46
Amodiaquin	1.953	1.716	1.608	0.0345	34

TABLE 4—APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME (ϕ_v), PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUME AT INFINITE DILUTION (ϕ_v°) AND S_v VALUES OF WATER AND DRUG SALTS

Water/Drug	ϕ_v ($ml mol^{-1}$)			ϕ_v° ($ml mol^{-1}$)			S_v
	293 K	298 K	303 K	293 K	298 K	303 K	
H ₂ O	-	-	-	18.03	18.05	18.07	-
Cyproheptadine hydrochloride	339.00	323.84	312.24				
	333.49	321.85	298.18				
	325.32	304.79	295.61	338.97	330.28	310.82	-225.88
	315.20	304.29	294.67				
	311.45	299.46	290.17				
Chlorpromazine hydrochloride	291.14	274.10	255.06				
	270.11	271.76	249.04				
	267.89	268.67	240.02	322.34	265.57	245.09	13.13
	262.36	261.46	239.31				
	261.90	261.35	229.21				
Ethambutol dihydrochloride	217.61	177.75	220.18				
	195.57	174.74	168.62				
	183.55	173.73	159.92	220.72	186.94	210.06	-128.38
	181.55	168.72	149.44				
	169.53	165.71	113.72				
Amodiaquin dihydrochloride	400.26	401.30	400.57				
	401.85	402.71	402.37				
	404.09	405.67	403.91	370.55	384.25	385.46	58.35
	404.97	406.51	405.17				
	405.77	407.24	406.45				
Pheniramine maleate	327.83	331.72	332.43				
	321.25	324.17	322.98				
	318.92	320.13	318.81	352.85	365.90	375.80	-183.52
	318.59	319.86	317.58				
	317.36	319.43	316.66				

TABLE 1—CONCENTRATION C , $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ AND DENSITY ρ VALUES FOR DRUG SALTS AT 293, 298 AND 303 K IN H₂O

C mol dm ⁻³	$(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$			ρ (g cm ⁻³)		
	293 K	298 K	303 K	293 K	298 K	303 K
Cyproheptadine hydrochloride						
0.004	0.1541	0.1340	0.1117	0.99828	0.99717	0.99584
0.005	0.1707	0.1475	0.1230	0.99832	0.99721	0.99595
0.0065	0.1925	0.1685	0.1422	0.99840	0.99741	0.99608
0.008	0.2127	0.1845	0.1535	0.99852	0.99745	0.99614
0.01	0.2363	0.2062	0.1737	0.99863	0.99754	0.99625
Chlorpromazine hydrochloride						
0.015	0.1719	0.1577	0.1392	0.99920	0.9983	0.9972
0.03	0.2385	0.2127	0.1976	1.0008	0.9996	0.9989
0.05	0.3088	0.2762	0.2535	1.0029	1.0018	1.0005
0.07	0.3575	0.3210	0.3023	1.0048	1.0037	1.0022
0.085	0.3962	0.3552	0.3313	1.0057	1.0045	1.0033
Ethambutol dihydrochloride						
0.0025	0.1421	0.1227	0.1075	0.99838	0.99735	0.99582
0.00375	0.1702	0.1455	0.1312	0.99859	0.99746	0.99609
0.005	0.1912	0.1675	0.1521	0.99864	0.99757	0.99627
0.01	0.2645	0.2325	0.2127	0.99917	0.99810	0.99796
0.02	0.3635	0.3212	0.2956	1.00039	0.99925	0.99896
Amodiaquin dihydrochloride						
0.07	0.2850	0.2649	0.2402	1.0028	1.0016	1.0003
0.085	0.3372	0.3074	0.2672	1.0034	1.0022	1.0009
0.10	0.3802	0.3442	0.3115	1.0046	1.0034	1.0021
0.12	0.4225	0.3823	0.3453	1.0055	1.0042	1.0032
0.14	0.4785	0.4350	0.3955	1.0066	1.0053	1.0041
Pheniramine maleate						
0.04	0.1385	0.1495	0.1622	0.9994	0.9981	0.9967
0.055	0.1628	0.1762	0.1921	1.0002	0.9989	0.9976
0.07	0.1880	0.2038	0.2213	1.0009	0.9997	0.9985
0.085	0.2095	0.2247	0.2412	1.0015	1.0003	0.9990
0.1	0.2235	0.2428	0.2648	1.0022	1.0008	0.9998

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

The B -coefficients of the salts (Table 2) have been found to be fairly high. These represent greater frictional force for the large sized electrolytes through the solution. For comparison, B -coefficients have also been determined using Vand's equation¹⁰,

$$\frac{C}{\log \eta_r} = \frac{2.303}{2.5\bar{V}} - \frac{2.303}{2.5} KC \quad (5)$$

where \bar{V} is the effective flowing volume obtained from the plot of $C/\log \eta_r$ against C and where $B = 2.5 \bar{V}$. The values of B are recorded in parenthesis (Table 2). The values of B -coefficient at different temperatures (Table 2) have been determined for better understanding of the structure-making or structure-breaking properties.